

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPOSITE FAIRING BAND ASSEMBLY FOR A STAINLESS STEEL SONAR DOME

Tamunoiyala S. Koko¹, Milton J. Connor² and Garry V. Corbett³

¹*Martec Limited, 1888 Brunswick Street, Suite 400, Halifax, N.S., Canada, B3J 3J8*

²*Composites Atlantic Limited, 71 Hall Street, Lunenburg, N.S., Canada, B0J 2C0*

³*DMSS 7-3-5, National Defence Headquarters, Ottawa, ON, Canada K1A 0K2*

SUMMARY: This paper describes investigations carried out to replace the stainless steel fairing band assembly components (including the fairing band, tail cap, and fasteners) for the C5 hull mounted sonar dome, with composite material. The study was motivated by the need to eliminate corrosion damage associated with the use of the stainless steel components. The investigation focused on material selection, component design, tooling and fabrication requirements for each of the components. It was shown that the fairing band assembly components could be fabricated from glass-epoxy composite materials using simple fabrication techniques such as hand layup and fasteners made of GRP material could be used to replace the non-critical stainless steel fasteners.

KEYWORDS: hull mounted sonar dome, fairing band, composite fasteners, glass reinforced plastics (GRP)

INTRODUCTION

This paper describes investigations carried out to replace the current fairing band assembly components of the C5 sonar dome with composite material. The dome has an aerofoil shape in plan and is approximately 4 m nose to tail, 1.3 m wide and 1.8 m high. Figure 1(a) shows a side view of the dome-hull interface. The dome is fastened to the flange of the dome spacer in the hull structure. The fairing band assembly is used to wrap around the dome-hull interface to provide a smooth surface, as shown in Figure 1(b), to reduce turbulence and noise. The existing fairing band assembly, comprising of the fairing band, tail cap and fasteners, is made of stainless steel material. In the presence of moisture, a cathodic corrosion mechanism is created between the stainless steel fairing band components and the mild steel dome spacer. The resulting corrosion ruins the mounting threads in the dome spacer which causes loss of the tail cap and fairing band. This requires the ship to be brought to dry dock, to perform appropriate corrective measures, thereby increasing the maintenance cost and reducing the operational readiness of the ship.

Because of their excellent corrosion resistant properties composites material are considered as suitable replacement materials for the stainless steel material to eliminate the corrosion problem. This study was undertaken to investigate the feasibility of using composite materials for the fairing band components. The investigations carried out to design and fabricate the composite fairing band, tail cap and fasteners are described in the following sections. Descriptions of the stainless steel components are first provided then, for each

component, investigations on the composite material selection, design and the tooling and fabrication requirements are provided. The challenges and lessons learned are also discussed.

DESCRIPTION OF STAINLESS STEEL COMPONENTS

Fairing Band

The fairing band is used to wrap around the sonar dome-to-hull interface, as shown in Figure 1, to provide a smooth surface in order to minimize flow disturbances. Figure 2 shows details of the fairing band. It is made of a stainless steel band which is 4.43 m long, 0.14 m wide and 0.89 mm thick. At one end of the fairing band is a latch block which fits into the front end of the dome-spacer in the hull structure. At the other end of the fairing band is a guide block which fits into the aft end of the dome spacer. The latch block and the guide block are fastened to the dome spacer by means of the fasteners designated as Types A and B. The fasteners are described below. Along the length of the band are seven space bars 19.05 mm x 9.525 mm x 73.025 mm welded to the band as shown in Figure 2. At the top and bottom of the band are 25.4 mm wide rubber gaskets for sealing the band against the hull and the dome. The stainless steel band can coil into a roll of approximately 0.914 m diameter for storage purposes.

Tail Cap

The tail cap component is a filler piece at the trailing ends of the fairing band to provide a smooth surface. Figure 3 shows the details of the tail cap component. It is made from a 200 mm x 140 mm x 0.89 mm stainless steel sheet formed to the shape of the dome at the aft end, as shown in the figure. The tail cap also consists of a stiffener and a solid bar which houses the fastener holes, and is attached to the dome spacer by means of two fasteners designated as Type C, which are described below. Strips of 25 mm wide rubber gaskets are bonded to the top and bottom surfaces of the tail cap for sealing against the dome and hull.

Fasteners

Three types of fasteners designated as Types A, B and C are used to fasten the fairing band and the tail cap components to the dome spacer in the hull structure. The dimensions and details of the fasteners are shown in Figure 4. Fastener Type A fits into the latch block at the front end of the fairing band. It is 38 mm long with 12.5 mm diameter 13 UNC screws. Fastener Type B fits into the guide block at the aft end of the fairing band. This fastener is 76.2 mm long and is fully threaded with 12.5 mm diameter 13 UNC screw threads. Finally, fastener Type C is used to fasten the tail cap sub-assembly to the ship hull. The fastener is 31.75 mm long and has 9.4 mm diameter 16 UNC screws.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL SELECTION

Fairing Band

Three composite material systems with glass, Kevlar, and high strength polyethylene (HSPE) fibers and epoxy resins were considered. These composite systems have several advantages and disadvantages for the present application. However, the material selection was based on -

cost; water absorption characteristics; ease of fabrication; and experience in marine environment. As the band is not a major structural component, it was sufficient to base the material selection on the above criteria, since other design criteria such as tensile strength, are expected to be satisfied by all three composites. In Table 1 the three composite materials are compared based on the selected criteria. Property data from Refs 1 and 2 were used for the comparison. As shown in the table, glass reinforced plastic (GRP) had several advantages over the Kevlar-epoxy and HSPE-epoxy systems. Hence, GRP was selected for this application.

Tail Cap

Because of the advantages of glass reinforced plastic (GRP) composites highlighted above GRP was also selected for the tail cap component.

Fasteners

Investigations were carried out to select suitable materials for the fasteners to be used to attach the fairing band and trailing cap to the stainless steel dome and mild steel ship hull. The main thrust was to select a material which was compatible galvanically with stainless steel, mild steel, and GRP used for the dome, hull, and fairing band/trailing cap, respectively. In order to avoid corrosion between any two components of the fairing band assembly, fasteners made of glass reinforced plastics were selected. Rather than fabricate these fasteners in-house, it was decided to purchase them from suitable suppliers, since cost was a major concern in the execution of this project. Consequently, some composite fasteners manufacturers in the United States were contacted and information on the types and capabilities of composite fasteners were obtained. The tensile and shear strengths of some glass reinforced composite fasteners from Cherry Textron [3] are compared with those of stainless steel fasteners. The shear strength of the PEEK/LQ (polyetheretherketone with long continuous quartz fiber) fastener is close to that of stainless steel, and was hence considered suitable for fastener Types A and C which are mainly loaded in shear. However, the glass reinforced fasteners could not be used for the fastener Type B because of the very large torque required to keep the fairing band flat against the dome. Hence for the Type B fastener, stainless steel with teflon coating was recommended.

DESIGN OF COMPONENTS

The approach adopted was to retain, as much as possible, the shapes and sizes of the fairing band, guide block, latch block and spacers, and replace the stainless steel material with GRP. This was necessary to reduce the amount of modifications to the ship hull-dome interface to accommodate the composite fairing band assembly. The significance of this was to keep the cost of installing the composite fairing band assembly low.

Fairing Band

Dimensions

The fairing band consists of a four-layer GRP strip 4.43 m long, 0.14 m wide. The thickness of the strip was 1.05 mm, which compares to the 0.88 mm thickness of the stainless steel band. With this thickness, the composite fairing band was flexible enough to wrap around the

gentle curve at the front end (See Figure 1) without matrix cracking. The fairing band stops short of the sharp curve at the trailing end. It is the tailing cap component which fits over this sharp curve (Figure 1). Two 25 mm wide strips of neoprene material were bonded to the top and bottom of the band on the inside face.

The guide block, latch block and spacer bars are constructed of GRP material and fabricated integrally and co-cured with the GRP fairing band to avoid secondary bond lines which would serve as areas of weakness. The dimensions and locations of the seven spacer bars are exactly the same as for the stainless steel spacer bars (Figure 2). The dimensions and shape of the composite guide block at the aft end are similar to the stainless steel block. However, a smooth transition with a 12.5 mm minimum radius is provided between the fairing band and the guide block to reduce stress concentrations.

The shape and dimensions adapted for the composite latch block required modifications to the hull dome spacer structure but eliminates the need for load bearing composite fasteners (Type A) at the front end. The modifications to the dome spacer required welding two 71 mm x 0.125 mm x 9.5 mm mild steel blocks to the web stiffeners at the front end of the dome spacer structure to provide wedges for the L-shapes GRP latch blocks. A schematic representation is shown in Figure 5. The space between the two composite latch blocks is to be filled by a 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm x 71.3 mm GRP block which is fastened to the dome spacer by a 9.5 mm diameter Type C composite fastener.

Stress Analysis

Figure 6 illustrates schematically how the tensile load is transferred from the tensioning bolts to the fairing band. During installation, the fairing band subassembly is fitted into the dome spacer by sliding the guide block between the alignment rails on the aft-end of the dome spacer. The fully threaded bolt (Fastener Type B) is backed off as much as possible to enable the front half of the fairing band to be attached to the dome spacer via the latch block. Then a torque of 40-54 Nm is applied to the fully threaded fastener to keep the fairing band tight against the dome. The torque produces a force against the dome spacer structure, which is transmitted to the fairing band via the guide block. The tensile force produced in the fairing band was estimated, using simple fastener equations [4,5], to be approximately 14.2 kN. With a safety factor of 1.5 and a 20 percent reduction of strength due to potential material degradation, the composite fairing band was found to be adequate with a large margin of safety.

Tail Cap

The trailing cap sub-assembly was fabricated as a single piece using a female mold having the shape of the trailing cap. The GRP tail cap has the same dimensions as the stainless steel cap. The main body of the tail cap consists of 4 plies of plain weave glass/epoxy prepreg. This provided a wall thickness of 1.05 mm which is close to the thickness of the stainless steel cap. The solid interior section consists of about 100 layers of plain weave GRP material.

Fasteners

Fastener Type A

The Type A fasteners fit into the latch block at the front end of the fairing band. However, with the modifications adapted for the composite latch block geometry there was no more need for the this fastener. The design required a 9.5 mm diameter GRP fastener to hold the GRP spacer block in between the two fairing band as illustrated in Figure 5. This fastener which is similar to the Type C fastener, did not carry any substantial loads and was designed only for nominal loads. Using the PEEK/LQ material and 9.5 mm diameter fasteners, the shear and tensile capacities of the bolt at installation are 25.8 kN and 13.4 kN, respectively. The fastener was treated with an adhesive thread locker to prevent it from backing off after installation.

Fastener Type B

The Type B fastener fits into the guide block at the aft end of the fairing band. This fastener was loaded mainly in tension. By the application of a torque, the fastener presses against the dome spacer structure. The axial load induced in the fastener is transferred to the fairing band via the guide block as illustrated in the free body diagram in Figure 6. The more torque applied the more the axial force and hence, the tensile force in the fairing band. The installation of the stainless steel fairing band assembly required a torque of 40-54 Nm to keep the fairing flat against the dome. A requirement for the design of the composite fairing band assembly was to provide a similar load in the fairing to ensure it stayed flat against the dome.

The torque capacity of the PEER/LQ fastener was approximately 8-10 Nm, which was significantly lower than the torque needed to induce the required tension in the fairing. In order to provide the required tension in the fairing band, stainless steel bolts with teflon coating were recommended for the Type B fasteners. The internal threads in the guide block were fabricated integrally with the fairing band by laying up the GRP on removable threaded inserts. Thus the threaded part of the teflon coated stainless steel fasteners was in contact with threaded GRP material in the guide block. Only the tip of the fastener contacted the mild steel spacer dome structure. The teflon coating on stainless steel bolt would reduce the likelihood of the generation of current between the dome spacer and the tip of the bolt, thereby reducing the possibility of corrosion damage to the fastener tip. The integrity of the threads in the GRP guide block was investigated by a simple pull-out test. Details of the experimental setup are provided in [6]. The threads sustained tensile loads greater than 34 kN without failure.

Fastener Type C

The Type C fasteners are used to fasten the tail cap sub-assembly to the ship hull. This fastener does not carry any substantial load and was hence designed for nominal loads. However, it should be noted that these fasteners screw into threaded holes in the mild steel spacer structure and have caused the most frequent corrosion damage. Hence a fastener made of composite material was essential. The PEEK/LQ fastener was used. The shear and tensile capabilities are respectively, 25 kN and 13 kN which wee adequate to hold the tail cap in place. The fastener was treated with an adhesive thread locker to prevent it from backing off after installation.

TOOLING AND FABRICATION

Fairing Band

The fairing band was fabricated from four piles of plain weave E-glass epoxy prepreg laid-up on a solid tool surface and cured with a pressure plate for even pressure distribution during cure. The flat bars, latch blocks, and guide blocks were integrally fabricated from many layers of the same material compacted and incorporated in the main lay-up. The dimensions and configurations were in accordance with the design presented above. The GRP fairing band was treated with a polyurethane coating to reduce the water absorption by the composite material. Also, a two coat antifouling agent was applied to reduce marine growth during service.

Tail Cap

The tail cap was fabricated from plain weave E-glass epoxy prepreg with the main body consisting of 4 plies, and a solid interior section consisting of a stack-up of many plies integrated with the main external plies. A female mold was used to lay up the tail cap. The two fastener holes in the tail cap were integrally fabricated using removable threaded plugs.

Fasteners

Since the fasteners were obtained from suppliers, there were no tooling or fabrication requirements for the fasteners in this study. The fastener holes in the fairing band and tail cap were integrally fabricated using removable threaded inserts as discussed in the previous two subsections.

SUMMARY

This report has provided a description of a study to replace the stainless steel fairing band assembly components (including the fairing band, tail cap, and fasteners) for the C5 hull mounted sonar dome, with composite material. The investigation focused on material selection, component design, and tooling and fabrication requirements for each of the components. Glass epoxy was selected as the replacement material to eliminate the corrosion problem associated with the use of the stainless steel components. The fairing band assembly components were fabricated from plain weave E-glass epoxy composite material using a simple fabrication technique such as hand lay up. Glass epoxy based composite fasteners were used to replace the stainless steel fasteners which sustained only nominal loads. However, it was not feasible to replace the high load-carrying stainless steel fasteners with composites fasteners because of their low torque capacities.

REFERENCES

1. Pussegoda, N., MacDonald, D., Murphy, J.G. and Malik, L., "The Effect of Environmental Exposure on the Properties of High Strength Polyethylene (HSPE) Fibre Composites," DREA CR/93/450, January 1993.
2. Niu, M.C.Y., Composite Airframe Structures, Practical Design Information and Data, ConmiLit Press Limited, Hong Kong, 1993.

3. Anon, Cherry Textron Technical Data on Advanced Composite Products, California, 1996.
4. Shigley, J.E. and Mitchell, L.D., Mechanical Engineering Design, 4th Edition, McGraw Hill Book Company, New York, 1983.
5. Langhner, V.H, and Hargan, A.D., Handbook of Fastening and Joining of Metal Parts, 1st Edition, McGraw Hill Book Company, New York, 1956.
6. Koko, T.S. and Connor, A.D., "Composite Fairing Band Assembly for the C5 Hull-Mounted Sonar Dome", Martec Report No. TR-96-23, Halifax, September 1996.

<i>Table 1: Comparison of Candidate Fairing Band Composite Materials</i>			
Property	Material System		
	GRP	Kevlar/Epoxy	HSPE/Epoxy
Water Absorption (Sea Water)(%)[1]	0.19	<1.0	0.32
Relative Cost *	1.00	4	> 4
Ease of Fabrication **	Good	Poor	Poor
Experience in Marine Environment	High	Low	Low

* Cost of fibre relative to E-glass [2], for comparison only

** Bonding between fiber and resin

<i>Table 2: Tensile & Shear Strengths of Stainless Steel & Selected Composite Fasteners [3]</i>				
Property	PEEK/L Q	Epoxy/L G	PEI/L G	Stainless Steel
Shear Strength, ksi	53	24	45	50
Tensile Strength, ksi	27	16	25	73

Notes:

PEEK/LQ = Polyetheretherketone with long (continuous) quartz fiber

Epoxy/LG = Epoxy with long (continuous) glass fiber

PEI/LG = Polyetherimide with long (discontinuous) glass fiber

Figure 1: Dome-Hull Interface

Figure 2: Details of Stainless Steel Fairing Band Assembly

Figure 3: Stainless Steel Tail Cap

Figure 4: Stainless Steel Fasteners

Figure 5: Modified Latch Block

Figure 6: Load Transfer from Tensioning Bolt to Fairing Band